

Citizen science as a resource to define threats to bathing on beaches. The case of jellyfish in Malaga.

Abstract: Study that characterizes the threat due to visits by swarms of jellyfish on the coast of the province of Malaga, Spain, one of the most touristic in Spain. To achieve this objective, it uses the data collected by the Infomedusa and Medusapp applications, in addition to the historical data collected in the jellyfish layer provided by the Andalusian regional government. A Geographic Information System is used for the geolocation and compilation of the data provided by the three sources. The result is maps where you can see the areas of the province most exposed to the arrival of jellyfish based on recorded historical data. The information generated is very useful and could be combined with beach carrying capacity maps for better risk management due to the arrival of jellyfish in the province.

Key words: Jellyfish - beaches - citizen science - applications -Malaga

1. INTRODUCCIÓN

Beach recreation and leisure activities are highly dependent on environmental conditions. These may be atmospheric (e.g. temperature or weather), coastal conditions (e.g. degree of accessibility, beach area, type of sand, etc.) or ocean mass. Factors related to the marine environment that may affect the use and enjoyment of beaches include: water quality, sea conditions and marine hazards. Among the latter, there are some threats that are known today, such as sharks, certain types of algae or jellyfish.

This work deals specifically with the phenomenon of jellyfish on the coast of the province of Málaga. Their massive appearance in the summer of 2018 caused inconvenience to beach users and bad press for the Costa del Sol as a tourist destination. The local authorities in the coastal municipalities of the province of Málaga were alarmed. Since then, they have been living with the fear that their beaches could once again become an area of jellyfish swarms.

Jellyfish are therefore a risk to the leisure and enjoyment of the beaches, as well as to the tourist activity itself. As with any risk, risk management strategies are needed to reduce it. Prevention is one of them. In this sense, there are approaches that model the occurrence of jellyfish two days in advance (Gutiérrez Estrada et al., 2021) and that partially predict the interannual variation (Bellido et al., 2020) of their proliferation. To date, however, there is no model that can accurately predict future situations such as those experienced in 2018. There have been many studies on the evolution and proliferation of jellyfish in southern Spain (Kienberger, Navarro & Prieto, 2016; Prieto & Navarro, 2013; Prieto et al. 2015; Prieto, 2018; Prieto, Astorga & Navarro, 2010; Prieto, Armani & Macías, 2013; Prieto), in which the main sources are sightings made by collaborators. In some cases, this work has been used by the regional administration of Andalusia to generate a georeferenced information layer with historical jellyfish sightings (Red de Información Ambiental de Andalucía, 2015).

In Spain, citizen alert networks have been set up to warn of their presence on the Spanish coast through mobile phone applications, as they can have a negative impact on the recreational use of beaches. Similar monitoring strategies have also been implemented in other countries to warn of risks on beaches. In South Africa, for example, there is an organisation called SharkSpotters that warns of the presence of sharks on beaches.

The cooperation of citizens through their warnings not only serves to alert, but also to generate knowledge about the phenomenon. In this way, data is generated through citizen science.

The collaboration between citizens and the scientific community, contributing to the analysis of a specific problem, constitutes what is known as citizen science (Senabre et al., 2018). The population involved in the analysis or data collection actively participates with a potential scientific benefit. This participation, which can be in the framework of a

research project or simply the desire to contribute to the solution of a danger or threat, is mainly carried out through the use of smart mobile devices and has become a new way of empirically processing information, mainly in the field of natural and experimental sciences (Wylie et al, 2014; Ferran-Ferrer, 2015).

Collaboration in this sense is very useful for a collective of citizens with common interests, forming part of the process and helping to mitigate undesirable situations (Danielsen et al, 2010). These techniques can be compared with other more traditional techniques led by specialists in the field in question, complementing them and providing an argument for their inclusion in scientific studies (Cohn, 2008; Irwin, 1995; Theobald et al., 2015). Although this research technique is very useful, Silvertown (2009) points out the need for validation of the data provided by the participating public, as well as the need for good design and standardisation so that the results do not lose quality.

With the widespread use of the internet and smartphones, these networks of engaged users have become more widespread and are particularly useful in the case of coastal threats, which are very useful for recording the presence or absence of certain species, both to protect endangered species (Conrad and Hilchey, 2010) and to control the spread and extent of invasive species (Palmer et al., 2017).

With regard to the problem of jellyfish arriving on beaches, among the existing mobile applications for the exchange of information between users on the state of the coastline, there are some platforms for collecting data on jellyfish sightings, some of which are very popular. These include iMedjelly (Marine Science Institute, 2020), Infomedusa (Aula del Mar, 2020), Grumering (Cabrer, 2018) and MedusApp (Blasco and Palacios, 2021). The data obtained with these have been used in some studies. Rubio-Gómez and Gutiérrez-Hernández (2020) use those from MedusApp (Blasco and Palacios, 2021) to map sightings along the Andalusian coast; de la Fuente et al. (2021) perform a similar exercise in the western half of the coast of the province of Málaga with those from Infomedusa (Aula del Mar, 2013), as do Souvirón et al. (2019) to follow the tracks of a swarm in the summer of 2018. Gutiérrez-Estrada et al. (2021) also include them in a predictive model.

Citizen science has thus provided a very important impetus for the characterisation of this phenomenon. Its records serve to generate knowledge about the phenomenon. This work joins the data generated by two applications, Infomedusa (Aula del Mar, 2013), Medusapp (Blasco and Palacios, 2021) and the georeferenced database of jellyfish sightings in the region of Andalusia (Junta de Andalucía). The main objective is to spatially characterise the threat of jellyfish arrivals to the Costa del Sol coastline.

This objective can be subdivided into the following subjective objectives

- To collect the data on jellyfish sightings from the available sources for the Costa del Sol (Junta de Andalucía, Medusapp and Infomedusa).
- To integrate all the data in a geographical information system.
- Classify and map the results.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodology aims to map the presence of jellyfish on the beaches of the province of Málaga during the summers of the period 2014 to 2020. To this end, two sources of information based on the concept of citizen science have been used: the Infomedusa (Aula del Mar, 2014) and Medusapp (Blasco, E., & Palacios, R. (2021) applications. Both were georeferenced and spatially aggregated to count the total number of sightings. The unit of analysis is the beach, specifically all those collected by the Infomedusa application, which in turn is based on the official list of beaches georeferenced by the Junta de Andalucía (Junta de Andalucía, 2021).

Given the heterogeneity of the sources used, the process of producing the final cartography requires the homogenisation of the data for its subsequent cartographic

representation. Based on this need, this methodological section first presents the sources used and then explains how the data were homogenised.

2.1. STUDY AREA

The study area is located in southern Spain, in the autonomous community of Andalusia, and includes the coastline of the province of Malaga, known as the Costa del Sol. This coastline is bathed by the Mediterranean Sea and extends over 162 beaches in 15 municipalities, with a total length of 185 kilometres of coastline (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Location of the study area
Source: Prepared by the authors.

2.2 CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOURCES

The Infomedusa and Medusapp applications record the messages sent by their users in different ways. These are two free applications that anyone can download onto their mobile phone. The use of the former is more limited to the province of Málaga and other nearby areas, while the latter is more widespread throughout Spain.

The data collected by Infomedusa is stored in a semi-structured database. The user must first select the beach from which he/she wishes to make his/her comment. Then he/she writes a free sentence. Many of these comments are made to ask other users about the state of the beaches, and others are registered to give descriptive information about the beaches themselves. Therefore, not all comments are positive warnings about the presence of jellyfish.

In the case of Medusapp, the records collected by this application are stored in a structured database containing fields with information on The user, the date, the beach where the observation was made, the size of the species or species sighted, the number of specimens and a text for free commentary by the user. Therefore, in the case of this database, unlike Infomedusa, all records correspond to sightings.

In particular, for the purposes of this work, it should be noted that there are differences both in the spatial and temporal recording methods, as well as in the type of information aggregated to characterise the recorded data.

At the spatial level: Medusapp and Rediam present the sightings cartographically with points along the coast. In the case of the former, it is a location that represents the GPS coordinates recorded by the mobile device from which the data are issued; in the case of the latter, it is a punctual location that should not be understood as absolutely precise,

but rather as a more or less central location over the sighting area in a cartography that was not originally designed to be displayed on a large scale.

In the case of Infomedusa, the sightings are recorded generically on the beach where the citizen informant is located, and the citizen selects it from the complete list of sandbanks displayed by the application. Therefore, in the case of this application, it should be understood that sightings on the same beach should be represented by a line rather than a point, as the exact coordinates from which the sighting reports are sent are unknown.

On a temporal level, there is homogeneity in the way data are recorded between Infomedusa and Medusapp, as both assign the day/month/year in the sightings, however Infomedusa started operating in 2014, while Medusapp started in 2018, so the data available for this work are based on those initially recorded by Infomedusa (2014), combined with those of Medusapp from 2018 onwards.

There are also differences in the information that accompanies the pure spatio-temporal data. Medusapp provides information on aspects such as the type of jellyfish and the number of specimens sighted (in a classification by intervals). Infomedusa, on the other hand, offers the user's raw commentary. This means that it is necessary to distinguish between those that correspond to sightings and those that do not. On the positive side, it is possible to derive information such as the (approximate) number of specimens and even the species.

2.3. HOMOGENISATION OF DATA AND CONSTRUCTION OF A SINGLE DATABASE

The method proposed in this study aggregates all the sightings from different sources into a single map for the whole province of Malaga, using beaches as the spatial unit of analysis.

The first step in the methodological process is to develop a strategy to homogenise the data in space and time, using the beach as the unit of calculation. The aim is to include all sightings in this unit of analysis without duplicating information. This is because the sources used place the sightings in the same time frame. For this reason, this process is divided into the following phases:

A) Delineation of beaches: for this purpose, the length information contained in the official database of the Ministry (MITECO (2021) is used and, as support, the geographical features observed in the Reference Spatial Data of Andalusia (Institute of Statistics and Cartography of Andalusia (2023) are used to delineate them.

b) Sum of sightings on each beach. In order to do this, it is first necessary to filter the information according to its source. To do this, a hierarchy of data prevalence was established. The Infomedusa records are considered as priority and the Medusapp records as complementary. The procedure then proceeds to the summation of the sightings from the two sources, which is divided into two parts.

First, all the sightings from Infomedusa on each of the beaches per year are added together. Only sightings on a single day are counted: if there are several sightings on a single day, only one is counted.

Secondly, all Medusapp sightings that do not coincide in time (on the same day) with those already added by Infomedusa are added to the total.

Once all the previous processes have been carried out, there is a unique georeferenced database of jellyfish sightings. The original databases of Infomedusa and Medusapp must be added to this database.

2.4. MAPPING REPRESENTATION

In a subsequent step, the single database created in the previous phase was used to present its information in two ways: in summary form for the entire coast of Málaga, and in point form, through maps, for each beach in the province. In this case, a database manager (MS Access) and a geographical information system (ArcGis) were used. Through them, queries were generated to summarise and present the information.

The attributes represented are:

- The number of messages received by each of the applications. This is to characterise the level of use of each of them.
- The number of sightings made. This gives a first approximation of the areas where more jellyfish have been reported.
- The number of days with jellyfish. This is a second level of approximation for characterising the jellyfish threat on beaches. It is possible for a single beach to receive many warnings on the same day, so this exercise tries to clarify this circumstance.
- The number of days with a high influx of jellyfish. This is a final step to characterise the beaches according to the severity of the threat.

In order to consider a day as a day with a high influx of jellyfish, a triple way was considered:

- (a) Events registered in Infomedusa that are understood as numerous by interpreting the literal content written by a user.
- b) Because it is an event registered in Medusapp with a value of more than 11 specimens in the quantity field.
- c) Because there are at least 4 different reports on the same beach on the same day, registered by one of the two applications.

3. RESULTS

The level of use of applications is much higher in the case of Infomedusa. The specific data are shown in Table 1.

	INFOMEDUSA (2014-2020)	MEDUSAPP (2018-2020)	TOTAL
MESSAGES (records)	76664	227	76891
MESSAGES that warn of jellyfish SIGHTINGS	4647	227	4874

Table 1. Level of use of the Infomedusa and Medusapp applications on the Malaga Coast in the period 2014-2020. Source: Prepared by the author based on Infomedusa and Medusapp.

For every jellyfish sighting report on Medusapp, Infomedusa issued 20 reports, sent from a total of 166 beaches, compared to 91 for Medusapp.

If the comparison is made only in the period when Medusapp was operational (2018-2020), the ratio is 11 to 1 in favour of Infomedusa (2591 sighting alerts versus 227 for Medusapp).

On the basis of the data recorded by both applications, it can be confirmed (Table 2) that jellyfish are present on the Málaga coast every year, although in very variable quantities that vary from year to year.

The years with the highest number of days with jellyfish presence in the period analysed were 2015 and 2018. The latter was the summer with the highest number of warnings, both total (2735) and those specifically related to high numbers of jellyfish (851).

Year	Days with a jellyfish warning	Number of jellyfish sighting reports	Number of warnings of large quantities of jellyfish
2014	20	34	6
2015	108	1265	398
2016	67	258	2
2017	90	499	98
2018	104	2735	851
2019	28	44	1

2020	26	39	0
Total	444	4874	1357

Table 2. Quantitative summary of days and total number of jellyfish sightings on the coast of Málaga in the period 2014-2020. Source: Prepared by the author based on Infomedusa and Medusapp.

Many of these warnings were issued on the same day, for example on 20 July 2018 alone there were 37 warnings of high jellyfish levels in the water issued from 20 different beaches in the municipalities of Estepona (1), Marbella (5), Benalmádena (1), Málaga (7), Rincón de la Victoria (2), Vélez-Málaga (2), Torrox (1) and Nerja (1).

Spatially, there are differences in the level of use of the applications along the coast.

In the case of Infomedusa, its use is widespread throughout the Costa del Sol. As can be seen in Figure 2 (Map 1), the messages were sent from a number of beaches covering almost the entire coastline. The central coastal strip, between Benalmádena (to the west) and Torre del Mar (to the east), has a very high concentration of messages. On the other hand, the coastal areas with the fewest messages are located at the most distant ends, both to the west and to the east, and in a small sector to the west of Fuengirola. Exactly the areas with the lowest contributions are the ones where Medusapp is free of jellyfish sightings or warnings. This similarity can therefore be explained simply by the fact that these are coastal areas with fewer bathers.

However, this parallelism does not apply to the beaches of the central urban areas of the province, which are known to be very frequented by bathers. In this stretch, the number of Medusapp reports seems to be lower than expected, especially when compared with map 5 in Figure 2, and it can be seen that the number of jellyfish sightings reports in this area of the coast is high, so by this logic there would be a lack of Medusapp reports in this stretch.

In the map of sightings (map 4 of figure 2), which does not differentiate the amount of jellyfish on the same day, a predominance of danger can be seen, with a higher concurrence in the central stretch of the coast, belonging to the coastal sector of the provincial capital. This circumstance extends, with slightly less intensity, to the adjacent stretches, with a much higher intensity towards the eastern beaches, from Rincón de la Victoria to Torre del Mar. In the eastern part of the coastline, which is generally less concentrated, there is a random distribution, with some stretches standing out in the municipalities of Torremolinos, from Los Álamos beach to La Carihuela beach, in Fuengirola (Los Boliches and Las Gaviotas) and some sectors in Marbella (stretch from Dunas de Artola beach to El Cable) and Estepona (La Rada).

The comparison of the latter map with those of application use (maps 1, 2 and 3 in Figure 2) suggests that there is an "excess" of comments in some areas, such as the central areas southwest of the city of Málaga and the sector between Málaga and Torre del Mar. The high level of use of the applications seen in Maps 1 and 2 in Figure 2 translates into a high number of sightings in Map 4. However, when these raw totals are adjusted in a map of sighting days (Map 5 in Figure 2), it can be seen that in some places with many comments (municipalities of Málaga, Rincón de la Victoria or Vélez-Málaga) the same result in sighting days could be achieved with a lower number of comments.

The good news is that this "excess" of comments, although "excessive" in terms of characterising the phenomenon in terms of time, is useful for making an approximation of the number of jellyfish that visited the beach on that particular day. In this way it can be seen that, in Map 6 of Figure 2, the coastal areas that experienced a greater number of days with a high jellyfish presence during the period studied are located in a continuum that runs from the centre-west of the city of Málaga, through Rincón de la Victoria, to the eastern end of the municipality of Vélez Málaga.

In other parts of the province, the highest values are found in the main towns. This is probably due to the greater number of messages transmitted in these areas, which are also the most popular beaches in the respective municipalities. This is the case in Manilva, Estepona or Marbella, Fuengirola (Los Boliches), Benalmádena or Torremolinos.

Figure 2. Representative maps of the level of use of the Infomedusa and Medusapp applications in the province of Malaga, and results of sightings and days of sighting. Source: Prepared by the author based on Infomedusa and Medusapp data.

4. DISCUSSION

The results obtained seem to be in line with previous work on the proliferation of jellyfish in the Alboran Sea.

Figure 2 compares them with the maps of 3 previous works: Rubio Gómez & Gutiérrez Hernández (2020) and Prieto & Navarro (2013), and the map of jellyfish sightings in the Andalusian coast published by the Environmental Information Network of Andalusia (2015).

The former classifies the coast according to the sightings recorded in Medusapp (Blasco & Palacios, 2021). From the latter, the map of sightings from 2012 was selected, the most abundant of those collected in the aforementioned work, almost all of which, moreover, are *Pelagia noctiluca*, the protagonist of the sightings in the case of the present research, with data from 2018. As can be seen, there is agreement that the areas with the most sightings are located in the city of Málaga and along the coast near Torre del Mar, which is also indicated in the map of the Andalusian Environmental Information Network (2015).

In addition, Prieto & Navarro (2013) indicate that there is an area of sightings in Marbella, which is also shown in the maps resulting from this work. In the coastal sector running from Torre del Mar to Torrox, there is a general coincidence in recording a higher level of sightings in Torre del Mar, but few sightings in the Torrox area (in the case of Prieto & Navarro, 2013) or sightings that are below average (in the case of Rubio Gómez & Gutiérrez Hernández, 2020). It should be noted, however, that the comparison of the results of the present research with these previous works is based on relative terms, since the sources used in each of them are different, with the present research using by far the most detailed and comprehensive source. The work of Prieto & Navarro (2013) is mainly based on information provided by environmental agents, while the work of Rubio Gómez & Gutiérrez Hernández (2020) is based on the Medusapp application (Blasco & Palacios, 2021), which is more popular in the Levantine area than in the Alboran Sea. This means that in the first study, the number of sightings is much lower (only those with a high abundance of jellyfish are counted), and in the second, the number of sighting records (209 from Medusapp) is ten times lower than that of Infomedusa only for 2018.

Comparison of the resulting hazard mapping with those obtained by Rubio Gómez & Gutiérrez Hernández (2020) and Prieto & Navarro (2013) and Red de Información Ambiental de Andalucía (2015). Source: Prepared by the author based on Infomedusa and Medusapp, Rubio Gómez & Gutiérrez Hernández (2020) and Prieto & Navarro (2013) and Red de Información Ambiental de Andalucía (2015).

Finally, although a priori there seems to be a correlation between the most popular beaches and those with the highest number of jellyfish sightings, both isolated and in swarms, this theory is also contradicted by the records of danger of beaches that are not overcrowded and far from the large urban circuits, such as Dunas de Artola and Maro.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Once the maps have been produced, the following conclusions can be drawn

The Infomedusa application is widely used in most of the province.

The Medusapp application does not seem to be sufficiently implemented on the Costa del Sol, at least during the period analysed.

The databases derived from the Infomedusa and Medusapp applications are an important source of information for the analysis of coastal phenomena such as jellyfish, especially when compared with the existing cartographies in the study area.

In the province of Málaga, the records collected for the years studied allow us to affirm that the stretch of about 50 km that runs between Benalmádena and Torre del Mar is the coastline with the highest number of days with jellyfish.

In terms of the number of jellyfish in the registered days of presence, it can be seen that the Western Axarquía coast, up to the provincial capital, will be the most affected during the period 2014-2020.

This is in line with the general perception of the jellyfish problem in the region, since in 2018 most of the news about the high influx of jellyfish referred to sightings of swarms in this eastern area of the province of Málaga.

At that time, the local authorities of the Costa del Sol showed their interest and great concern about this phenomenon and its possible consequences in areas such as tourism. Therefore, the characterisation of the phenomenon with sources such as those used in this work is a necessary step for its proper management. This work is a contribution in this sense.

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